

CHAPTER 5

Understanding the magnetic, spin-based optical and transport properties of $K_2W(Cl/Br)_6$ for spintronic, photovoltaic and thermoelectric applications

In this chapter, we have discussed the magnetic, spin-based optical and transport properties of $K_2W(Cl/Br)_6$ by using first-principles calculation. Firstly, we have discussed about the structural properties of these compound such as lattice parameter, tolerance factor, and octahedral factor with phase stability. Then, the stable magnetic configuration of these two compounds is discussed. Also, the Heinsberg model has been adopted to estimate the Curie temperature of titled compounds. Thereafter, we have spin-polarized band structure and density of states of $K_2W(Cl/Br)_6$. Then, the spin-polarized optical properties of $K_2W(Cl/Br)_6$ are discussed. In the last section, the spin-polarized optical properties of $K_2W(Cl/Br)_6$ are discussed.

5.1 Computational details

The magnetic and transport properties of K_2WX_6 ($X = Cl, Br$) are investigated by Wien2k and BoltzTraP code [103]. The structural optimization is performed with PbEsol functional. Further, mBJ functional has been taken into consideration for accurate prediction of electronic band gap on which exchange splitting and transport properties are dependent [104]. For the energy convergence, we have considered K-mesh of order 12x12x12 which is equivalent to 2000 k-points. Furthermore, the product of maximum wave vector and muffin tin radii is kept as $R_{MTX}K_{max} = 8$, along with angular momentum vector $l = 10$ and Gaussian factor = 10 . We have obtained the level of convergence of 10^{-5} Ry self consistently by using above mentioned inputs. In the end, we have calculated spin-based transport properties in terms of Seebeck coefficient, electrical and thermal conductivities and figure of merit by using BoltzTraP code [103].

5.2.1 Structural properties

The vacancy ordered lead free double halides perovskite K_2WX_6 have stable face centred cubic structure with space group Fm3m (225). The perspective view of K_2WX_6 is illustrated in figure

5.1. The vacancy between the octahedra W (Cl₆/Br₆) are occupied by K⁺ whereas each octahedra is separated by 12-fold coordination system of Cl/Br. In this structure, each K⁺ ion is bonded with 12 X⁻ ions whereas every W⁺ is coordinated to 6 Cl⁻/Br⁻ ions. Moreover, each W (Cl₆/Br₆) is located at the corner and face centre of cubic system. The Wyckoff positions for Cs, W, X are (0.25, 0.25, 0.25) (0, 0, 0,) and (x, 0, 0), respectively.

Figure 5.1: The crystal structure and polyhedral form of K₂WX₆ (X = Cl, Br) with magenta (K), blue (W), and green (X).

For the confirmation of stability of K₂WX₆ in cubic phase, we have computed Goldsmith tolerance factor (t_G) through the relation

$$t_G = \left(\frac{r_K + r_X}{r_W + r_X} \right) \quad (6.1)$$

Where r_K , r_W and r_X are the ionic radii of K, W and X ions, respectively. The reported values of t_G are found to be 0.98 and 0.96 for K₂WCl₆ and K₂WBr₆, respectively. To investigate synthetic possibility of K₂WX₆, we have calculated the enthalpy of formation of these two systems by using following equations

$$H_f = E_{\text{total}}(\text{K}_2\text{WX}_6) - 2E_K^{\text{bulk}} - E_W^{\text{bulk}} - 6E_X^{\text{bulk}} \quad (6.2)$$

Figure 5.2: Volume optimization curve of K_2WX_6 ($X = Cl, Br$).

Where $E_{total}(K_2WX_6)$ is the ground state energy of K_2WX_6 , E_K^{bulk} , E_W^{bulk} and E_X^{bulk} are the energies of K, W and X in their bulk form [105]. The obtained values of ΔH_f are -31.12 eV and -27.12 eV for K_2WCl_6 and K_2WBr_6 , respectively. The negative ΔH_f represent the formation reaction of K_2WCl_6 and K_2WBr_6 are exothermic. Such types of reaction evident the possibility of synthesis of K_2WCl_6 and K_2WBr_6 . The energy optimization plots of K_2WCl_6 and K_2WBr_6 are shown in figure 5.2 (a, b). The least ground state energy is obtained from FM ordering of both systems implies this ordering is most favorable. In addition, we calculated energy T_c by using Heisenberg model i.e., $T_c = 2\Delta E/3xK_B$, where x is the contribution of W and ΔE is the energy difference between ferromagnetic and antiferromagnetic ground state i.e. $\Delta E = E_{AFM} - E_{FM}$. The T_c values of K_2WCl_6 and K_2WBr_6 are found to be 613 K and 597K, respectively. The high T_c values make these compounds suitable for spintronic applications.

5.2.2 Band structure of $K_2W(Cl/Br)_6$

The half metallic ferromagnetic material having high spin polarizability (P) are essential for spin based electronic applications [106, 107, 108, 109, 110, 111, 112, 113, 114, 115, 116, 117, 118, 119, 120]. The polarizability (P) can be calculated through the following equation

$$P = \frac{DOS_{up} - DOS_{dn}}{DOS_{up} + DOS_{dn}} \times 100\% \quad (6.3)$$

Where DOS_{up} and DOS_{dn} are the density of states of at Fermi level in up and down channel, respectively. The spin polarized band structure is presented in Figure 5.3, which shows the overlapping quantum state with E_F in the spin up channel of K_2WCl_6 and K_2WBr_6 which makes them metallic. In the spin down channel, the valance band maxima (VBM) and conduction band minima (CBM) lie at same k point with finite separation, making them direct band gap semiconductor. Thus, K_2WCl_6 and K_2WBr_6 have 100 % spin polarization. The band gap values of K_2WCl_6 and K_2WBr_6 are found to be 3.01 eV and 2.72 eV, respectively. Also, the obtained total magnetic moment (μ_{tot}) is $2\mu_B$. The integer values of total magnetic moment imply they are half metallic in nature which is highly desirable for spintronic applications.

Figure 5.3: The spin polarized band structure of K_2WX_6 ($X = Cl, Br$).

5.2.3 Density of states of $K_2W(Cl/Br)_6$

In order to clarify the origin of half metallicity in K_2WCl_6 and K_2WBr_6 , we have performed the density of states analyses which is shown in figure 5.4. It is noticeable from the TDOS that K_2WCl_6 and K_2WBr_6 have half metallic nature which is consistent with band structure results.

Further, the partial density of states clearly shows that W-d orbital is mainly responsible for the half metallic character in K_2WX_6 . The crystal field due to W-X Coulomb interaction split 5d states of W into t_{2g} and e_g . The t_{2g} is triply degenerate (d_{xy} , d_{yz} , d_{zx}) comparatively lower energy than the double degenerate e_g (d_z^2 , $d_{x^2-y^2}$). The splitting of e_g results raises in the energy of $d_{x^2-y^2}$ and lower in the energy of d_z^2 . The half metallic ferromagnetism in K_2WX_6 is originated by double exchange mechanism between W atoms via X atom.

Figure 5.4: Total and partial density of states of K_2WX_6 ($X = Cl, Br$).

5.2.4 Spin-based optical properties of $K_2W(Cl/Br)_6$

Motivated by electronic properties, we have calculated the spin-based optical properties of $K_2W(Cl/Br)_6$. First of all, we have calculated the characteristics of $\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, \alpha$ and σ for up channel. It is clearly noticeable from figure 5.5 (a) that there is a higher value of ϵ_1 at zero incoming photon energy which is obvious because of metallic nature of this channel. However, there is negative value of ϵ_1 at 0.2 eV which is due to higher plasma frequency of material than the incoming photon frequency. Above this energy, there low value of ϵ_1 which is almost constant over the energy for both compounds. In figure 5.5 (b), we have shown the

characteristics of ε_2 as a function of incoming photon energy. It is worthy to mentioned here that ε_2 reflects the phenomena of electronic transition from valance band to conduction band which basically govern the absorption property of a material. It is noticeable from this figure 5.5 (b) has higher value of ε_2 at zero incoming photon energy for both compounds which is obvious because of metallic nature of up channel. For metal we need zero energy for electronic transition. However, the detailed studies shows that ε_2 above 1.7 eV for both compounds and thus there will be low absorption of these materials above this energy value. Further, we have calculated the absorption coefficient ε_2 . The absorption spectra of up channel of both systems are in figure 5.5 (c) . It is observed that both compounds have non zero values of α at zero incoming photon energy. However, this value is low at intermediate energy. Finally we have shown the reflectivity as a function of incoming photon energy and observed that higher value of it in the low energy. The higher value of reflectivity is again due to metallic nature of this channel.

Figure 5.5: The temperature dependent (a) ε_1 , (b) ε_2 , (c) α , and (d) R of up channel of $K_2W(Cl/Br)_6$

Due to promising electronic properties of down channel of $K_2W(Cl/Br)_6$, their optical are calculated. We have calculated the characteristics of $\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, \alpha$ and σ for down of $K_2W(Cl/Br)_6$ channel. It is clearly noticeable from figure 5.6 (a) that there is a appreciable value of static dielectric constant i.e. $\epsilon_1(0)$. However, the details analysis revealed that K_2WBr_6 has higher $\epsilon_1(0)$ than that of K_2WCl_6 due to its smaller band gap. This result is perfectly consistent with Pennn's model. The appreciable $\epsilon_1(0)$ values of $K_2W(Cl/Br)_6$ demonstrated that they have good defect tolerance capability. In figure 5.6(b), we have shown the characteristics of ϵ_2 as a function of incoming photon energy for down channel of both compounds. It is worthy to mentioned here that ϵ_2 reflects the phenomena of electronic transition from valance band to conduction band which basically govern the absorption property of a material. It is noticeable from this figure 5.6 (b) ϵ_2 is having zero value at $E = 0 eV$. However, the minimum value of energy needed for electronic transition is $2.99 eV$ and $1.99 eV$ for K_2WCl_6 and K_2WBr_6 . These are the optical band gap of respective compounds. Also, we can notice from figure 5.6 (b) that there is rapid increment of ϵ_2 beyond their optical band gap and take a peak value at certain in coming photon energy and then there is further decrement which is the typical nature of ϵ_2 for semiconducting channel. Further, we have calculated α as a function of incoming photon energy as shown in figure 5.6 (c) which shows that beyond optical band gap both compounds have higher order absorption coefficient which is highly required for photovoltaic cell. Finally, we have calculated R as a function of incoming photon energy which is shown in figure 5.6 (d). It is clear from this figure that the down chanel of both compounds is having lower R due to their semiconducting nature. Altogether, the higher α with low R revealed that the spin down channel of both compounds favor for the construction of high efficiency solar cell. So, on has to polarize the sample in the down configuration by applying field.

Figure 5.6: The temperature dependent (a) ϵ_1 , (b) ϵ_2 , (c) α , and (d) R of down of $K_2W(Cl/Br)_6$

5.2.5 Spin-based thermoelectric properties of $K_2W(Cl/Br)_6$

Presently, most of the energy requirement are fulfilled by fossil fuels which is non-renewable. But due to the unlimited demand of energy, the globe is in grief of energy crisis. Therefore, researcher have devoted much time for the exploration of those materials which can directly produce electrical energy from wasted heat. In this perception, the thermoelectric material has attracted substantial interest due to their efficient capability to convert wasted heat into electricity. The thermoelectric materials are useful for power generation in diverse applications in energy-based devices.

The performance of a thermoelectric material can be given by dimension less parameter known as Figure of merit (Z_T); $ZT = S^2\sigma T / (k_e + k_l)$, where S , σ , T , k_e , and k_l are Seebeck coefficient, electrical conductivity, temperature, electrical part of thermal conductivity, and lattice part of thermal conductivity. A good thermoelectric material should have ZT value close to unity which is only possible when it has high S , σ and low k_e . In this work, we have examined the spin-based transport properties of K_2WX_6 by using BoltzTraP code.

First of all, we have calculated the lattice thermal conductivity of $K_2W(Cl/Br)_6$ using Slack equation that is shown in figure 5.7. We can see that the lattice thermal conductivity K_l decreases with increasing the temperature.

Figure 6.7: Temperature K_l calculated through Slack equation.

The rate of charge flow can be deduced from electrical conductivity (σ). On the basis of charge flow, the material is categorized into three types i.e., metal, semiconductor and insulator. A good thermoelectric material should have high σ . The spin based σ versus temperature plots for K_2WCl_6 and K_2WBr_6 are shown in Figure 6.8 (a) and Figure 5. 9(a), respectively. The detail analyses revealed that σ in spin up channel decreases with temperature and attain lowest values of $1.97 \times 10^5 \Omega^{-1} m^{-1}$ (K_2WCl_6) and $2.25 \times 10^5 \Omega^{-1} m^{-1}$ (K_2WBr_6) at 600 K. On the other hand, the spin down channel has very less value and maintain constant values up to 400 K. Beyond this limit, there is an σ increases at very high rate with temperature. The decrease trend of σ with temperature in metallic channel and increase in semiconducting channel is common in half-metallic material.

The total thermal conductivity (k) is the sum of electrical part plus lattice part i.e. $k = k_e + k_l$. The variation k directly affects the performance of a thermoelectric material on the basis of heat conversion efficiency [ZT]. A good thermoelectric material should have ultra-low k to attain ZT value close to unity. We have calculated k_e by using BolzTraP code. For lattice conductivity (k_l) calculation we have employed Slack equation. On the other hand, Figure 5.8 (b) and Figure 6.9 (b) clearly demonstrated that in the spin up channel k_e has a direct relation

with temperature where it rises to $3.41 \text{ W k}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-1}$ and $4.12 \text{ W k}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-1}$ for K_2WCl_6 and K_2WBr_6 up to 400 K. Beyond this limit, k_e has decrease trend with temperature for both compounds. In the spin down channel, k_e maintain almost constant up to 450 K and above this temperature k_e increases abruptly with temperature. This implies that the contribution of k_e at higher temperature is more for both systems. The spin based Seebeck coefficient (S) is presented in Figure 5.8 (c) and Figure 5.9 (c) for K_2WCl_6 and K_2WBr_6 . It is noticeable that S for up channel increases with temperature. The values of S for up channel are found to be $11.1 \mu\text{V K}^{-1}$ (K_2WCl_6) and $21.8 \mu\text{V K}^{-1}$ (K_2WBr_6) at 600 K. On the other hand, negative S values in the down channel implies n-type nature of K_2WCl_6 and K_2WBr_6 . Altogether, the obtained S values are favour for SSE technology.

The product of S^2 and electrical conductivity (σ) gives power factor (PF) which illustrate the performance of a thermoelectric device. The spin varied PF is studied and presented in Figure 5.8 (d) and Figure 5.9 (d). It is observed that spin up PF increases with temperature. The obtained PF values are noticed to be 12.0×10^9 (K_2WCl_6) and 13.2×10^9 (K_2WBr_6) at 600 K. For spin down channel, the PF values are noticed to be constant up to 400 K. Beyond this limit, PF increases abruptly with temperature for both systems. The high values of PF make these compounds suitable for thermoelectric technology.

Figure 5.8: Spin dependent (a) σ , (b) k , (c) S , and (d) PF of K_2WCl_6 as a function of temperature.

Figure 5.9: Spin dependent (a) σ , (b) k , (c) S , and (d) PF of K_2WBr_6 as a function of temperature.

The efficiency of thermoelectric generator is deduced from ZT values. The spin dependent ZT of K_2WCl_6 and K_2WBr_6 are presented in Figure 5.9 (a, b). In spin down channel, the ZT rises with temperature and found to be 0.05 and 0.042 at 600 K for K_2WCl_6 and K_2WBr_6 , respectively. In spin down channel, the ZT decrease linearly with temperature. The ZT values at 600 K are recorded as 0.95 and 0.86 for K_2WCl_6 and K_2WBr_6 , respectively.

Figure 6.9 Spin dependent ZT of (a) K₂WCl₆ and (b) K₂WBr₆

5.3 Summary and Conclusion

In conclusion, we have systematically investigated the structural, electronic and transport properties of K₂WX₆ [X = Cl, Br]. The negative formation energy confirmed that K₂WX₆ can be experimentally synthesized while tolerance factor closes to unity demonstrated that stable cubic phase of same systems. We have obtained the T_c values of 613 K and 597K for K₂WCl₆ and K₂WBr₆, respectively. The spin polarized electronic band structure and density of states shows the 100 % spin polarization of K₂WX₆. The half-metallic nature along with high Curie temperature demonstrated that they are promising spintronic materials. Further, the calculated spin based optical properties shows that the down channel of both compounds is having higher order of absorption coefficient and low reflectivity which tells that we can use them for high efficiency solar cell by polarizing in down channel direction. The thermoelectric parameters are calculated to examine the suitability in spin based Seebeck effect. The high σ , S, PF, ZT and low thermal along the spin down channel demonstrated that we can use them for high efficiency thermoelectricity by polarizing in down channel direction.